

Dance Written

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Material to support Dance Written, a chapter in the 2021 Brill publication titled: Deconstructing the Shiva Nataraja. New Research in Multidisciplinary Perspective.

Dance Written is an account of how Śiva's dancing figure is described in *Pratiṣṭhā* manuals, written for a chapter in the 2021 Brill publication titled: Deconstructing the Shiva Nataraja. New Research in Multidisciplinary Perspective.

In that chapter, there was space only for English translations of the material under discussion. Here are supplied the Sanskrit passages from which those English translations were drawn. Plus an edition and translation of the account of the dancing Śiva given in the *Piṅgalāmata*, another early northern text.

Nāṭyaśāstra 10.61c-65b on the *Vaiśākhasthāna*:

<i>tālās trayo 'rdhatālas ca pādayor antaram bhavet</i>	10.61cd
<i>tālāms trīn ardhātālāms ca niṣpannoruṃ prakalpayet</i>	
<i>tryaśrau pakṣasthitau caiva tatra pādau prayojayet</i>	10.62
<i>vaiśākhasthānam etad dhi skandaś cātrādhidaivatam</i>	
<i>sthānenānena kartavyam aśvānāṃ vāhanaṃ budhaiḥ</i>	10.63
<i>vyāyāmo nirgamaś caiva sthūlapakṣinirūpaṇam</i>	
<i>śarāsanāsamutkarṣe vyāyāmakṛtam eva ca</i>	10.64
<i>recakeṣu ca kartavyam idam eva prayokṭṛbhiḥ</i>	10.65ab

There should be three and a half *tālas* between the feet. And one should make the thighs three and a half *tālas* apart. One should set the feet pointing to the side at an angle. This is the *Vaiśākhasthāna*. Skanda is its presiding deity. The wise use this *sthāna* for riding horses, exercise, setting forth, playing the part of a large bird, and in the exertion of drawing tight the bow string. It is also used by dancers, in *Recaka* foot movements.

Mohacūrottara 2.88b-95 on the *Vaiśākhasthāna*:

<i>nṛtteśaḥ¹ kathyate 'dhunā</i>	
<i>nṛtyarudraṃ prakurvīta candrārdhakṛtamastakam</i>	2.88bcd

¹ nṛtteśaḥ] FG; nṛtyeśaṃ H

<i>vaiśākhasthānakadharaṃ² nāgayajñopavītinam</i>	
<i>saumyānanam jaṭājūṭadhāriṇam³ vyālamekhalam</i>	2.89
<i>pīnavakṣorujaghanam⁴ sarvalakṣaṇasamyutam</i>	
<i>dvīpicarmadharaṃ⁵ sādho vṛṣārūḍham smitānanam</i>	2.90
<i>sumadhyaṃ ṣoḍaśābhujam kuryād vā dvibhujam śubham</i>	
<i>veṇuvīṇāmṛdaṅgādivādyasaṃghoṣaśobhitam</i>	2.91
<i>vāmaṃ prasāritabhujam dvitīyaṃ abhayapradam</i>	
<i>akṣasūtreṣudaṅḍāsiśūlaśaktivaraṅkaraiḥ</i>	2.92
<i>kapālapāśakhaṭvāṅgakheṭacarmāṅkuśāṅvitam</i>	
<i>ekaṃ cāpadharaṃ tadvat prasāritam athottaram</i>	2.93
<i>bhavyā brahmā⁶ hariḥ skando⁷ nandī kālādayaś ca ye</i>	
<i>vīkṣamāṇāḥ⁸ śivaṃ nṛtyaṃ bhṛṅgī kāryo 'grataḥ sthitaḥ⁹</i>	2.94
<i>mālākhaḍgabhr̥to ye tu siddhā yakṣādayas tathā</i>	
<i>bāhyasthāś ca¹⁰ prakartavyā nṛtteśaḥ¹¹ kathitas tava</i>	2.95

Next is described the Lord dancing (*Nṛteśa*). One should make the dancing Rudra with a crescent moon at his head. He holds the *Vaiśākhasthāna*, and has a snake as a sacred thread. His expression gentle, he wears his dreadlocks in a knot, and a snake as a necklace. With muscled chest, thighs and buttocks, and every requisite feature, smiling, he wears a tiger skin, and rides a bull, O noble one. One should make him slim-waisted, with sixteen arms, or two arms is fine. He is glorified by the sound of flute, lute, drum, and more. A left arm is extended out (*prasārita*), the second (right) one offers a gesture of reassurance (*abhaya*). His other hands hold a rosary, arrow, stick, sword, trident, spear, boon, skull, noose, skull-topped club, shield, hide, and goad. And one holds a bow, extended out to the left side. Bhavyā, Brahmā, Hari, Skanda, Nandī, Kāla, etc. gaze on the dancing Śiva. Bhṛṅgī stands in front. Bearers

² vaiśākha] FH; vaiśākhyā G • sthānakadharam] G; sthānakamdharan H; sthānakamdharan F

³ jaṭājūṭa] FH; jaṭākūṭa G

⁴ vakṣoru] F; vākṣoru GH

⁵ dvīpi] FG; dvīpi H

⁶ brahmā] FH; brahma G

⁷ hariḥ skando em.; hariskando FGH

⁸ vīkṣamāṇāḥ em.; vīkṣyamāṇāḥ FGH

⁹ kāryogrataḥsthitāḥ] H; kāryogratāsthitāḥ G; kāryograhataḥsthitāḥ F

¹⁰ bāhyasthāś ca] em.; bāhyasthācca FH; bāhyasthā G

¹¹ nṛtteśaḥ] FG; nṛtyeśaḥ H

of garlands and swords, and *siddhas* and *yakṣas*, etc. should be set on the periphery. The *Ṛṭteśa* has been described to you.

Kiraṇa tantra 52.39-41a on the *Vaiśākhasthāna*:

<i>kuryād rudraṃ susaukhyasthaṃ daśabāhuṃ trilocanam</i>	
<i>jaṭāmakuṭacandrārdhaṃ vyālayajñopavītinam</i>	52.39
<i>vyāghracarmaparīdhānaṃ ṛṭtaṃ ca saṃsthitam prabhum</i>	
<i>vaiśākhasthānasamyuktaṃ sāyudhaṃ vyālamekhalam</i>	52.40
<i>evaṃvidhaṃ bhavet saumyaṃ</i>	52.41a

One should make Rudra serene, with ten arms and three eyes. There is a sickle moon in his dreadlock crown. He wears a snake as a sacred thread. Clothed in tiger hide, the Lord stands dancing. With his weapon attributes and snake girdle, he is in *Vaiśākhasthāna*. The benign form is thus.

Piṅgalāmata 4.206 -213b on *Vaiśākhasthāna*:

<i>nāṭeśvaraḥ prakartavyaḥ prāk ṣaumye ca nirmitaḥ</i>	
<i>kiṃtv asau tāṇḍavārambho¹² bhujair bahusamākulah</i>	4.206
<i>adhordhavadiggatās te tu daśādau yāvad diggatāḥ¹³</i>	
<i>viśākhasthānacaraṇa aṅghrāsādilāsyadhṛk</i>	4.207
<i>prasphurad vadanaṃ śubhram ānamraṃ mastakonnataḥ</i>	
<i>jaṭābandhena dvau kāryau bhujau dvau cordhvacarmadhṛk</i>	4.208
<i>anyau dvau tālikākāryau dvau cānyau śūlakhaḍgadadhṛk</i>	
<i>khaṭvāṅgodyatapāṇiṃ ca kapālakṛtahastakaḥ</i>	4.209
<i>karaṇair drutalayādyaiś cārucārīgatādiśaḥ</i>	
<i>evaṃ jñātvā prakartavyaṃ bhujasaṃkhyānurūpataḥ</i>	4.210
<i>nandī dakṣiṇatas tadvan murajavādyatatparaḥ</i>	
<i>vāmataḥ kālah¹⁴ saṃlikhya vaṃsavādyasanṛtyakaḥ</i>	4.211
<i>vīṅvādanagāndharvāḥ¹⁵ sanṛtyā gaṇanāyakaḥ</i>	
<i>bhṛṅgyādya bāhyataḥ sarve nṛtyageyasamanvitāḥ</i>	4.212
<i>kārayen nāṭyarūpaṃ tu sarvālaṅkārabhūṣitam</i>	4.213ab

¹² tāṇḍavārambho] A; tāṇḍavārambhaḥ B

¹³ yāvaddiggatāḥ] em.; yāvadiggatā AB

¹⁴ kālah] em.; kāla AB

¹⁵ gāndharvāḥ] em.; gāndharvā AB

The Lord in dance form should be made as before, in his tranquil mode. But, he is engaged in dancing (*tāṇḍavārambhaḥ*), and has many arms. Those [arms] go up and down, all around. There are ten or more, in all directions.

His feet are in *Viśākhasthāna*. He moves in the *aṅgahrāsa* step, etc. His face is inclined and flashes radiant. He is crowned.

Two arms should be made to meet his dreadlocks. Two hold up a hide. Two others show their palms, and two more wield trident and sword. One hand raises a skull-topped club (*khaṭvāṅga*). And one holds a skull-bowl (*kapāla*). His hands move in the quick-time, etc., of charming dance gestures. Knowing this, one should make [the figure] according to the number of his arms.

Nandin is to his right, engaged in playing a drum.

To the left is Kāla, playing music, sounding a flute and dancing.

[There are] *gandharvas* playing the *vīṇā*, and dancing *gaṇas*.

And Bhṛṅgin, etc. are beyond. All are dancing and singing.

One should make the dancing figure adorned with every accoutrement.

Ajitāgama 36.229-233c on *Bhujaṅgatrāsa*:

<i>śvetavarṇaṃ prasannāśyaṃ dvīpacarmakṛtāmbaram¹⁶</i>	
<i>kiṅkiṅkṛtanāgendraṃ bakapicchadharaṃ tathā</i>	36.229
<i>viprakīrṇajāṭabhāram apasmāropari sthitam</i>	
<i>dakṣiṇena tu pādena kuñcitenetareṇa tu</i>	36.230
<i>jānvantam uddhṛtenāpi pānyantaṃ lambitena ca</i>	
<i>virājantaṃ caturhastam abhayaṃ dakṣiṇe dadhat</i>	36.231
<i>duṇḍubhiṃ cānyabhāge tu vahnim ekena cāparam</i>	
<i>prasāritakaraṃ tiryaggītanṛttaṃ janārdana</i>	36.232
<i>bhujaṅgatrāsam ity uktaṃ vāme gaurīsamanvitam</i>	
<i>ekāsanasthayā vāpi</i>	36.233abc

White in colour, gracious of face, clothed in tiger hide, the king of snakes as his anklet, he wears crane feathers. His dreadlocks strewn, he stands upon Apasmāra, with his right leg bent, and the other lifted up to the knee and pendant to the hand. Lustrous, four-armed, to the right he grants security (*abhaya*) and holds a drum. To the other side he holds fire in one

¹⁶ The Bhatt edition selects *dvīpa* (elephant) over *dvīpa* (tiger). Since other accounts favour a tiger skin, I emend to *dvīpa*.

hand, and the other extends across in lyrical movement (*prasāritakara, tiryaggītanṛtta*), O Janārdana. The form is called *Bhujāṅgatṛāsa*. Gaurī stands to his left, or she shares his throne.

Ajitāgama 36.233d-235 on *Sandhyā*:

<i>sandhyānṛttam athocyate</i>	36.233d
<i>dakṣiṇaṃ susthitaṃ pādaṃ vāmapādaṃ tu kuñcitam</i>	
<i>dakṣiṇe 'bhayaṭaṅkau ca pāśanāṅgau ca vāmake</i>	36.234
<i>dadhac caturbhir hastaiś ca jaṭāmakuṭasaṃyutam</i>	
<i>idam anyan nṛttarūpaṃ tṛtīyam adhunocyate</i>	36.235

The *Sandhyā* dance is described next. He stands on his right leg, and the left leg is bent. He has four hands: to the right are a gesture of security (*abhaya*) and a hatchet, and to the left he holds a noose and snake. He has a crown of matted locks. This is another dancing form. Next a third will be described.

Ajitāgama 36.236-238b on *Daṇḍapāda*:

<i>vāmaṃ tu kuñcitaṃ kiṃcid apasmāropari sthitam</i>	
<i>anyapādaṃ śirodeśe cordhve daṇḍavad uddhṛtam</i>	36.236
<i>viṃśaddhastasamopetaṃ sūlādyāyudhasaṃyutaṃ</i>	
<i>vīṇādivādyaśaṃyuktaṃ daṇḍapādādam iti smṛtam</i>	36.237
<i>nṛttarūpaṃ tridhā bhinnaṃ bhaved evaṃ janārdana</i>	36.238ab

The left leg is somewhat bent, and stood upon *Apasmāra*. The other leg is raised like a stick up above the head to a height of twenty *hastas*. Accompanied by weapons beginning with the trident, and with musical instruments such as the *vīṇā*, it is called the *Daṇḍapāda*. The dancing form should be thus divided into three types, O Janārdana.

Rauravāgama 35.249b-256a on *Uddaṇḍanṛtta*:

<i>uddaṇḍam adhunocyate</i>	
<i>triyakṣaṃ cāṣṭahastaṃ ca dvipādaṃ kṣīrasannibham</i>	
35.249bcd	
<i>jaṭāmukuṭasaṃyuktaṃ nāgendvarkaṃ ca dhutturam</i>	

<i>nānāvarṇāmbair yuktaṃ sarvābharāṇasaṃyutam</i>	35.250
<i>savakraṃ dakṣiṇaṃ pādamaṃ apasmāropari sthitam</i>	
<i>uddhṛtaṃ vāmapādaṃ cāpy uṣṇīṣordhvārkamātrakam</i>	35.251
<i>abhayaṃ śūlapāśaṃ ca ḍamaruṃ dakṣiṇe kare</i>	
<i>ghaṅṭāṃ caiva kapālaṃ ca ḍolaṃ caivāgnipātrakam</i>	35.252
<i>aṅguṣṭham uddhṛtāṅghres tu karṇād bhānudvayāṅgulam</i>	
<i>jaṅghāmadhyāt tu bāhvantar bhānvaṅgulam udāhṛtam</i>	35.253
<i>jānos tu ḍolābāhvagraṃ dvādaśāṅgulam iṣyate</i>	
<i>lambāntarāgrasūtrasya pārśvād evaṃ vidhīyate</i>	35.254
<i>vāme gaurīsamāyuktam ubhayor hastayor api</i>	
<i>skandaṃ dhṛtvā tu lajjādhyām iṣad vai lambitānanām</i>	35.255
<i>uddaṇḍam evam ākhyātam</i>	35.256a

Now the *Uddaṇḍa* is described. Milk-white, he has three eyes, eight arms and two legs. In his crown of dreadlocks are a snake, moon, sun and datura flower. He wears every ornament and garments of many colours. His bent right leg stands on Apasmāra. His left leg is raised to a height of twelve *aṅgulas* above the *uṣṇīṣa*. To the right side, he offers the gesture of security (*abhaya*) and holds a trident, noose and drum. [To the left] one hand swings (*ḍola*), and [the others hold] a bell, skull, and dish of fire. The big toe of the raised [left] leg is twice twelve *aṅgulas* from the [left] ear. There are twelve *aṅgulas* from the middle of the [left] shin to the [left] armpit. The tip of the [left] swinging hand is twelve *aṅgulas* from the [right] knee in height, projection and displacement to the side. To his left is Gaurī, carrying Skanda in both arms. Overcome with modesty, she lowers her face a little. Thus is the form called *Uddaṇḍa*.

Rauravāgama 35.256b-262c on Atyuddaṇḍanṛtta:

<i>atyuddaṇḍam athocyate</i>	
<i>svataḥ svavasthiṃ vāmapādam abje 'nyam ūrdhvagam</i>	35.256bcd
<i>dviraṣṭakasamāyuktaṃ jaṭāmakuṭamaṇḍitam</i>	
<i>ḍamarukābhayavajraṃ ca śūlaṃ pāśaṃ tathaiva ca</i>	35.257
<i>ṭaṅkaṃ daṇḍaṃ ca nāgaṃ ca dakṣiṇe 'ṣṭabhuje bhavet</i>	
<i>ḍolaṃ gajopamaṃ cāgniṃ mithunaṃ valayaṃ tathā</i>	35.258
<i>dhūṣadvayaṃ ca ghaṅṭāṃ ca kapālaṃ vāmapārśvake</i>	
<i>prāg uktaṃ pūrvasūtraṃ tu vāmapārśve prasārayet</i>	35.259
<i>nīvraṃ vedāṃśataḥ sarve prāg ivaiva prakalpayet</i>	

<i>vāmapārśve sthitam skandam savyahastodgataṃ natam</i>	35.260
<i>karaṇḍamakuṭopetā sarvābharaṇabhūṣitā</i>	
<i>gaurī caivaṃ tu vāme tu hy anyatra carmamunḍinī</i>	35.261
<i>nṛttaṃ karoti sa hy evaṃ ṛṣayaś cāmarāḥ sthitāḥ</i>	
<i>nṛttaṃ evaṃ samākhyātaṃ</i>	35.262abc

Next the *Atyuddaṇḍa* is described. At ease, his left foot on the lotus base, the other is raised. With a dreadlock crown, he has twice eight [arms]. In the eight arms on the right side are a drum, gesture of security (*abhaya*), thunderbolt, trident, noose, hatchet, stave, and snake. On the left side are the arm that swings like [the trunk of] an elephant (*ḍola, gajopama*), fire, a couple, a ring, a pair of cows, a bell, and a skull. One should extend the cord out to the left side, as was described above. As before, one should make all [the figures there] four parts high (*vedāṃśataḥ*)¹⁷. To the left side stands Skanda, as tall as the [lowermost] left hand. Gaurī is also to the left, with a *Karaṇḍa* crown, and every adornment. Or else there is Durgā. One makes the dancing figure thus. The sages and immortals attend. Thus is the dancing figure taught.

Rauravāgama 35.222-230 on *Bhujāṅgatrāsa*nṛtta:

<i>tryakṣam caturbhujam śāntam dvipādam ca jaṭādharā</i>	
<i>susthitam dakṣiṇam pādāpasmāropari sthitam</i>	35.222
<i>tasya jānvantam uddhṛtya vāmapādam tirastalam</i>	
<i>patākā dakṣiṇe haste vāmahastam tu vartitam</i>	35.223
<i>prakoṣṭhe tu patākāyām sapatram pannagam nyaset</i>	
<i>ḍamaruṃ savyahaste tu vāmahaste 'gnim uddharet</i>	35.224
<i>karṇāntam dakṣiṇe sūci hikkāntāgnikarāgraham</i>	
<i>hikkāntam syāt patākāgram nābhyantam jānur uddhṛtaḥ</i>	35.225
<i>tajjānuparivṛttasya maṇibandhāntaram manuḥ</i>	
<i>tajjāṅghādakṣiṇe haste madhyāgrāntam bhavet</i>	35.226
<i>ardhacandram tu dhuttūram nāgam sphītiśiras tathā</i>	
<i>bakapakṣasamāyuktaṃ bhānupuṣpayutaṃ śiras</i>	35.227
<i>tanavas tu jaṭābhārā jaṭāgre jāhnavīm dharet</i>	
<i>dakṣiṇe tāṃ vinā vāpi śiraścakrasamanvitam</i>	35.228

¹⁷ I choose to translate as four parts rather than a quarter of the height. A similar choice arises in the *Mayamata* account of the *bhujāṅgatrāsa*, where the goddess is assigned either 3 parts or a third. Again I choose 3 parts. Further below the *Kāmikāgama* account of the *bhujāṅgatrāsa* clearly gives 1 part to the aureole base.

<i>kuṇḍalaṃ dakṣiṇe karṇe patraṃ vai vāmakarṇake</i>	
<i>dakṣiṇe karṇapuṣpaṃ vāpy ubhayor api caiva vā</i>	35.229
<i>vyāghracarmottarīyaṃ ca kṛṣṇacarmāmbair yutam</i>	
<i>prabhāmaṇḍalasaṃyuktam apasmāropari sthitam</i>	35.230

Three-eyed, four-armed, tranquil, two-legged, wearing matted locks, on his right leg he stands firm upon Apasmāra. Lifting his left leg up to a horizontal at knee level, he makes a *Patākā* gesture¹⁸ at his [lower] right hand, and the [lower] left one is caused to turn (*varṭita*). At the forearm of the hand in *Patākā*, one should set a hooded snake. He holds a drum in the [upper] right hand, and fire in the [upper] left. The level of the [upper] right hand is at the ear; the hand carrying the flame is at throat height. The tip of the [right hand] *Patākā* reaches the level of the throat. The [left] knee is raised to the height of the navel. There are fourteen [*aṅgulas*¹⁹] between the bend of that knee and the [left] wrist. That hand being to the right of the [left] shin, its tip reaches to the middle [of that left shin]. His head is dressed with a sickle moon, a datura flower, a snake with its hood flared, the wing feathers of a crane, and plantain flowers. His dreadlocks are splayed. At the end of his hair, on the right side, he carries Gaṅgā, or else he is without her. He has a *śiraścakra*²⁰. There is an ear-ring at his right ear, a leaf at the left. Or there is a flower at the right ear, or else at both. He wears dark skins, with an upper garment of tiger skin. He has a *prabhāmaṇḍala*²¹ around him, and stands on Apasmāra.

Mayamata 36.67c-72b on *Bhujaṅgalalita*:

<i>nṛttaṃ bhujaṅgalalitaṃ sandhyānṛttaṃ ihocyate</i>	36.67cd
<i>ḍamaruṃ cāpi vahniṃ ca dakṣiṇe ‘dakṣiṇe kare</i>	
<i>triśūlaṃ paraśuṃ khaḍgaṃ bāṇaṃ syād dakṣiṇe kare</i>	36.68
<i>kheṭakaṃ ca pinākaṃ ca daṇḍaṃ pāśaṃ ca vāmataḥ</i>	
<i>cārucārīpracāreṇa prajvalaccaraṇānvitam</i>	36.69
<i>dakṣiṇaṃ kuñcitaṃ pādaṃ vāmaṃ jānvantam uddhṛtam</i>	

¹⁸ The *patākā* gesture noted here is clearly a hand position. It is not possible to know whether or not it correlates with the *patākā* hand position taught in modern classical dance.

¹⁹ An *aṅgula* is a finger breadth.

²⁰ The *śiraścakra* is a disc element flat to the back of the head.

²¹ The *prabhāmaṇḍala* is a halo-like frame around the figure.

<i>jānubāhyādipārṣṇyantam ekāditrimukhāntaram</i>	36.70
<i>tadantare 'ṣṭabhāge tu navadhā nirgamaṃ matam</i>	
<i>nirgamaṃ vāmapādaṃ tu yuktyā tatra prayojayet</i>	36.71
<i>rjvāgatamukhaṃ kiñcit kāyaṃ vai satribhaṅgikam</i>	36.72ab

The dance form that is the *Bhujāṅgalalita* [or] the *Sandhyā* is described next. A drum is in the right hand and fire in the left. Trident, axe, sword and arrow are in the right hands. Shield, bow, staff and noose are on the left. His feet dazzle with the graceful movement of the step. The right leg is bent. The left is lifted to the knee. There are from one to three [*aṅgulas*] between the front of the [right] knee and the [left] heel. That gap being divided into eight parts, the projection to the front is nine parts. One should effect the projection at the left leg correctly. His faces somewhat to the front, with a triple bend of his body.

Mayamata 36.72c-80b on Bhujāṅgaṭrāsa:

<i>sābhayaṃ dakṣiṇaṃ hastam aṅguṣṭhāntaṃ stanāntakam</i>	36.72cd
<i>udyadḍamarukaṃ hastam karṇacūlyantam uddhṛtam</i>	
<i>gajahastopamaṃ vāmaṃ vāmapādāntikaṃ gatam</i>	36.73
<i>sāgnivāmakaraṃ bāhumātroccaṃ kārayet sudhīḥ</i>	
<i>bāhukakṣāntaraṃ tāvat vyāghracarmadharāḥ samaḥ</i>	36.74
<i>vāme 'vāme phaṇī kṛtvā nyased vāme 'bhayaṃ tu vā</i>	
<i>saṃvikīrṇajaṭābhāraṃ bakapakṣavicitritam</i>	36.75
<i>karoṭimālayā yuktaṃ jaṭājūṭasacandrakam</i>	
<i>saṃvikīrṇajaṭāsaṃkhyā pañcasaptanavoditā</i>	36.76
<i>vāme gaurī tribhāge tu avāme nandikeśvaraḥ</i>	
<i>nṛttavādyādimuditaṃ nṛttabhṛṅgī ca pūrvakam</i>	36.77
<i>devadānavagandharvasiddhavidyādhārāṅvitam</i>	
<i>pārśvayor munibhir yuktaṃ suravṛndaniṣevitam</i>	36.78
<i>pīṭhastho 'thāmbujastho vā sthāpayet tannirantaram</i>	
<i>pādādhāram apasmāraṃ bhujāṅgaṭrāsam īritam</i>	36.79
<i>nṛttapūjāphalaṃ sadyaḥ śatrunāśakaraṃ bhavet</i>	36.80ab

The right hand offers the gesture of reassurance (*abhaya*), with the thumb tip at the chest. The rising drum hand [on the right] is lifted to the [right] earlobe. The left arm, like an elephant's trunk (*gajahasta*), reaches toward the left foot. The wise man should make the [other] left hand, holding the

fire, at shoulder height. Squared at the shoulders, he wears a tiger skin. One places a snake to right and left²². Or one may instead set the gesture of reassurance on the left side. He wears his dreadlocks as scatter, decorated with crane wing feathers, and a garland of skulls. The moon lies in his twisted dreads. The number of scattered strands of hair is five, seven or nine. To his left is Gaurī, at three parts high (*tribhāge*). To his right is Nandikeśvara. They delight to dance and music, etc., as does the dancing Bhṛṅgin, in front of him. To his sides are gods, demons, *gandharvas*, *siddhas*, *vidyādhara*s and sages²³. He is attended by a host of deities. One should establish him either on a base or on a lotus. Apasmāra is right under his foot. The *Bhujāṅgatrāsa* has been described.

Kāmikāgama 46.1-13b and 43c-50 on *Bhujāṅgatrāsa*:

<i>nṛttamūrtipratiṣṭhāṃ tu vakṣye tallakṣaṇānvitām</i>	
<i>caturbhujas triṅetraś ca saṃvikīrṇajaṭāyutaḥ</i>	46.1
<i>jaṭāmaḥṣaṣyukto vakranāgaphaṇāvṛtaḥ</i>	
<i>prṣṭhagāḥ pārśvagās tāḥ syuḥ pañcādyekaikavṛddhitaḥ</i>	46.2
<i>triṅśatsaṃkhyāvasānāḥ syur jaṭās tāḥ sāntarālakāḥ</i>	
<i>dhuttūrāgavadhārkādipuṣpayuktāḥ sapiṅgalāḥ</i>	46.3
<i>kṛtāñjalipuṭopetajāhnavyā dakṣiṇasthayā</i>	
<i>bālacandreṇa saṃyukto vāmapārśvasthitena ca</i>	46.4
<i>yukto vakulamālābhir muktādāmoragādibhiḥ</i>	
<i>vyāghrājīnāambaro dīptaḥ sarvābharaṇabhūṣitaḥ</i>	46.5
<i>vāmadormūlamālāmbidvīpicarmāambarānvitaḥ</i>	
<i>divyāambarānvito vāpi mṛgājīnayuto ‘pi vā</i>	46.6
<i>kasthabrahmakapālena nānāpuṣpair alaṃkṛtaḥ</i>	
<i>dhṛtavārāhadantāgrah śārdūlanakhakacchapaiḥ</i>	46.7
<i>śāṅkhikair maṇibhiḥ protamālayā hṛdi bhūṣitaḥ</i>	
<i>sthito dakṣiṇapādena vāmenoparivartinā</i>	46.8
<i>kuñcitāvartamānāṅghriḥ suprasāritatatkaraḥ</i>	
<i>ambikāmukhabiṃbābjabhramarikṛtalocanaḥ</i>	46.9
<i>ābaddhakiṃkiṇīyuktas tadvan nūpuraśobhitaḥ</i>	
<i>vāmadakṣiṇakarṇāḍhyapatrikānakrakuṇḍalaḥ</i>	46.10
<i>dakṣābhayakarasthena bhujāṅgenotphaṇena ca</i>	
<i>vāmāparakarasthena vahninā dakṣakena tu</i>	46.11

²² The snakes may be around the forearm, as at the *Rauravāgama* above, and *Kāmikāgama* below.

²³ The *gandharvas*, *siddhas* and *vidyādhara*s are semi-divine figures.

<i>ḍiṇḍimena samāyukta upavītena saṃyutaḥ</i>	
<i>gokṣīradhavalaprakhya ādityāṅgulabhaṅgayuk</i>	46.12
<i>nānāsarpaśamāyuktas tv apasmāropari sthitaḥ</i>	46.13ab
<i>dvibhujāś ca dvinetraś ca ūrdhvakāyas tv adhomukhaḥ</i>	46.43cd
<i>vyālaṃ vai vāmahaste tu tasyamūrdhā tu dakṣiṇe</i>	
<i>āvṛtālaṃkṛtābhaṅgī savyapārśvasīroyutaḥ</i>	46.44
<i>devasya vaktramānena jāhnavyāyāma ucyate</i>	
<i>dvibhujā ca triṇetrā ca karaṇḍamakuṭānvitā</i>	46.45
<i>sarvābharaṇasaṃyuktā kṛtāñjalipuṭānvitā</i>	
<i>ūrdhvabhāgād adhobhāgaṃ toyakāreṇa kārayet</i>	46.46
<i>gaṅgādevyānaya devas saṃyukto vā vivarjitaḥ</i>	
<i>prabhāvakaśavistāro daśādhikataśatāṅgulam</i>	46.47
<i>saptatṛiṃśacchatāyāmas taddaṇḍo bhāgavistaraha</i>	
<i>ekādi daśaparyantaṃ mātrair ūṇādhikāpi vā</i>	46.48
<i>dvyāṅgulād aṅgulārdhāt tu bālacandras tu saptadhā</i>	
<i>tadvaśāt pārśvagāṃ devīm kalpayet tadvidhānataḥ</i>	46.49
<i>kuryād bhṛṅgiriṭiṃ vātha bhadrakālīm athāpi vā</i>	
<i>bhujaṅgātrāsa ākhyāto bhujāṅgalalitas tataḥ</i>	46.50

I will describe the establishment of the dancing figure, with its required features. He has four arms, three eyes and scattered locks of hair. With a crown of dreadlocks, he is haloed by the hood of a coiled snake (*vakranāgaphaṇāvṛta*). Behind and to each side there should be from five to thirty strands of tawny hair, increasing one at a time, outspread. In the hair are datura, *aragvada* and *arka* flowers, etc., with Gaṅgā on the right side making an *añjali* gesture, and a crescent moon on the left side. He wears garlands of *vakula* flowers, etc. and strings of pearls, snakes, etc. Clothed in a tiger skin, he is lustrous with every accoutrement. A tiger-skin garment drapes from his left shoulder. Or he wears a bright garment, or a deer skin. At his head is the skull of Brahmā. He is adorned with all sorts of flowers, boar tooth, tiger claw and tortoise shell. At his chest he is embellished with a garland strung with shell beads. Standing on his right leg, with the left leg lifting up, the [left] leg is bent and turned. That [left] hand extends out (*suprasārita*). His eyes are drawn like bees to Ambikā's lotus-face. He wears a string of bells and an anklet. His right ear is bejewelled with a crocodile ear-ring, the right with one in the form of a leaf. Bearing a snake with its hood flared, his right hand dispels fear (*abhayakarastha*). The other left hand holds fire. In the other right hand is

a drum. He wears the sacred thread. Milk white, [his waist] has a curve of twelve *aṅgulas*. With many snakes, he stands on Apasmāra. [Apasmāra] has two arms and two eyes. His body is turned up, but his face turns down. In his left hand is a snake, the head of which is in his right hand. He is twisted, with his head turned to his left. In length, Gaṅgā equals the size of the god's face. She has two arms, three eyes, and a *karaṇḍa* crown. She has every embellishment, and her hands are in *añjali* gesture. Water flows from her upper part to the lower. The god may or may not be accompanied by the goddess Gaṅgā. The breadth of the space within the *prabhā* [*maṇḍala*] is 110 *aṅgulas*. The height is 137. Its stem is one part wide (*bhāgavistara*). Or there may be from one to ten measures less, or more. The crescent moon is seven-fold, from two *aṅgulas*, increasing by half an *aṅgula* at a time. One should make the goddess to the side [of the god], and according to his design. Or one sets Bhṛṅgiraṭi or Bhadrakālī [there]. [This design] is called the *Bhujaṅgatṛāsa*. Next is the *Bhujaṅgalalita*.

Kāmikāgama 46. 51-55c on *Bhujaṅgalalita*:

<i>bhujaṅgatṛāsavat sarvaṃ viśeṣaḥ kaścid asti hi</i>	
<i>uddhṛtasya talaṃ kuryāt sthitajānurdhvataḥ kramāt</i>	46.51
<i>dvimātraṃ vā trimātraṃ vā caturmātraṃ athāpi ca</i>	
<i>bhujaṅgalalitaḥ khyātas tadbhairava ihocyate</i>	46.52
<i>bhujaṅgatṛāsavat sarvaṃ viśeṣas tatra cocyate</i>	
<i>uddhṛtaṃ dakṣiṇaṃ pādaṃ vāmapādaṃ tu vā nayet</i>	46.53
<i>sa pādo dehamadhyasthaś cordhwapādatalānviṭaḥ</i>	
<i>caturbhujō 'ṣṭahasto vā nānādivyāstrabhūṣitaḥ</i>	46.54
<i>śilādidravyam āsādya kuryād evaṃ naṭeśvaram</i>	
<i>itthaṃ lakṣaṇamākhyātaṃ</i>	46.55abc

Everything is like the *Bhujaṅgatṛāsa*, but there is a distinction. The sole of the lifted [foot] is 2, 3, or 4 *aṅgulas* above the knee of the standing leg, by degrees. The *Bhujaṅgalalita* has been declared. Next is its *Bhairava* version. Everything is like the *Bhujaṅgatṛāsa*, but a difference is given. One may make the right foot raised, or else the left foot. That foot reaches the centre of the body, with the sole of the foot upturned. The figure may have four arms or eight, with various splendid weapons. Having gathered

the materials, in stone, etc., one makes the Naṭeśvara thus. These are its characteristics.

Dīptāgama 16.134c-136a on *Bhujaṅgalalita*:

ḍamaruṃ dakṣiṇe haste vāmahaste dhṛtānalam 16.134cd
triśūlaṃ paraśuṃ khadgaṃ vajrabāṇaṃ tu dakṣiṇe
khetakaṃ nāgapāśaṃ ca daṇḍaghaṇṭā śarāsanam 16.135
bhujaṅgalalitaṃ hy etad 16.136a

In the right hand is a drum; the left holds fire. On the right are trident, axe, sword, thunderbolt, and arrow. [On the left] are shield, snake, noose, bell, stick, and bow. This is the *Bhujaṅgalalita* form.

Dīptāgama 16.136bcd on *Bhujaṅgāñcita*:

bhujaṅgāñcitam ucyate
tad evaṃ vāmadakṣiṇyaṃ hastadaṇḍapatākayā 16.136bcd

The *Bhujaṅgāñcita* image is described next. The same as above, but with a flag and flagstaff to left and right.

Dīptāgama 16.137-139b on *Bhujaṅgatrāsa*:

uddhṛtaṃ vāmapādaṃ tu jānvantaṃ syād viśeṣataḥ
kuñcitaṃ dakṣiṇaṃ pādān evaṃ evaṃ prakalpayet 16.137
gajahastopamaṃ bāhūrāstīraṃ gatam +++
abhayaṃ dakṣiṇaṃ hastaṃ ḍamarukānalasaṃyutam 16.138
bhujaṅgatrāsam etad dhi tridhā bhedena kārayet 16.139ab

As a distinguishing feature, the left foot is raised to knee level. The right leg is bent. One should make it thus. [The left] arm, like an elephant trunk (*gajahastopama*), crosses the chest. The right hand bestows security (*abhaya*). [The other right hand] holds a drum. [The other left] holds fire. This is the *Bhujaṅgatrāsa* form.